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New Ideas On Super Stable By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Decompositions In Cancer's Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph

Henry Garrett · Independent Researcher · Department of Mathematics ·
DrHenryGarrett@gmail.com · Manhattan, NY, USA

1 ABSTRACT

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a Stable-Decompositions pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a \text{ and } E'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a \text{ and } E'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a \text{ and } V'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a \text{ and } V'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called an Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the

conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme
SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if
it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic
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SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; an Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions
SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic
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such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Extreme
power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
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SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; a Neutrosophic
V-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic
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Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; an Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. In this scientific research, new setting is introduced for new SuperHyperNotions, namely, a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Two different types of SuperHyperDefinitions are debut for them but the research goes further and the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass based on that are well-defined and well-reviewed. The literature review is implemented in the whole of this research. For shining the elegancy and the significancy of this research, the comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are featured. The definitions are followed by the examples and the instances thus the clarifications are driven with different tools. The applications are figured out to make sense about the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. The "Cancer's Recognition" are the under research to figure out the challenges make sense about ongoing and upcoming research. The special case is up. The cells are viewed in the deemed ways. There are different types of them. Some of them are individuals and some of them are well-modeled by the group of cells. These types are all officially called "SuperHyperVertex" but the relations amid them all officially called "SuperHyperEdge". The frameworks "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" are chosen and elected to research about "Cancer's Recognition". Thus these complex and dense SuperHyperModels open up some avenues to research on theoretical segments and "Cancer's Recognition". Some avenues are posed to pursue this research. It's also officially collected in the form of some questions and some problems. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Then δ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is a maximal of SuperHyperVertices with a maximum cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the (Neutrosophic) cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$: there are $|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperDefensive; a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is a maximal Neutrosophic of

SuperHyperVertices with maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$ there are: $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive. It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions more understandable. For the sake of having Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. It's redefined a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if the mentioned Table holds, concerning, "The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" with the key points, "The Values of The Vertices & The Number of Position in Alphabet", "The Values of The SuperVertices&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The Edges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The HyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The SuperHyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Endpoints". To get structural examples and instances, I'm going to introduce the next SuperHyperClass of SuperHyperGraph based on a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. It's the main. It'll be disciplinary to have the foundation of previous definition in the kind of SuperHyperClass. If there's a need to have all SuperHyperStable-Decompositions until the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then it's officially called a "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" but otherwise, it isn't a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. There are some instances about the clarifications for the main definition titled a "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions". These two examples get more scrutiny and discernment since there are characterized in the disciplinary ways of the SuperHyperClass based on a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" and a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's redefined "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" if the intended Table holds. And a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions are redefined to a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" if the intended Table holds. It's useful to define "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions more understandable. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses if the intended Table holds. Thus SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are "Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite", and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel" if the intended Table holds. A SuperHyperGraph has a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" where it's the strongest [the maximum Neutrosophic value from all the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions amid the maximum value amid all SuperHyperVertices from a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.] SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. A graph is a SuperHyperUniform if it's a SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. It's SuperHyperPath if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; it's SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperStar it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperBipartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's SuperHyperMultiPartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's a SuperHyperWheel if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. The SuperHyperModel proposes the specific designs and the specific architectures. The SuperHyperModel is officially called "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". In this SuperHyperModel, The "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperVertices" and the common and intended properties between "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperEdges". Sometimes, it's useful to have some degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy, and neutrality to have more precise SuperHyperModel which in this case the SuperHyperModel is called "Neutrosophic". In the future research, the foundation will be based on the "Cancer's Recognition" and the results and the definitions will be introduced in redeemed ways. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions or the strongest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. For the longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, called SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and the strongest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. There isn't any formation of any SuperHyperStable-Decompositions but literarily, it's the deformation of any SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form. A basic familiarity with Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions theory, SuperHyperGraphs, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs theory are proposed.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are some ideas in the featured frameworks of motivations. I try to bring the motivations in the narrative ways. Some cells have been faced with some attacks from the situation which is caused by the cancer's attacks. In this case, there are some embedded analysis on the ongoing situations which in that, the cells could be labelled as some groups and some groups or individuals have excessive labels which all are raised from the behaviors to overcome the cancer's attacks. In the embedded situations, the individuals of cells and the groups of cells could be considered as "new groups". Thus it motivates us to find the proper SuperHyperModels for getting more proper analysis on this messy story. I've found the SuperHyperModels which are officially called "SuperHyperGraphs" and "Extreme SuperHyperGraphs". In this SuperHyperModel, the cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperVertices" and the relations between the individuals of cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperEdges". Thus it's another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on the "Cancer's Recognition". Sometimes, the situations get worst. The situation is passed from the certainty and precise style. Thus it's the beyond them. There are three descriptions, namely, the degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality, for any object based on vague forms, namely, incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The latter model could be considered on the previous SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperGraph but it's officially called "Extreme SuperHyperGraphs". The cancer is the disease but the model is going to figure out what's going on this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The recognition of the cancer could help to find some treatments for this disease. The SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the "Cancer's Recognition" and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the forms of alliances' styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix "SuperHyper" refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Extreme SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general models. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Extreme SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the optimal SuperHyperStable-Decompositions or the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in those Extreme SuperHyperModels. Some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Extreme SuperHyperPath s have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a

SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. There isn't any formation of any
 SuperHyperStable-Decompositions but literarily, it's the deformation of any
 SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form.

Question 2.1. *How to define the SuperHyperNotions and to do research on them to find the “amount of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions” of either individual of cells or the groups of cells based on the fixed cell or the fixed group of cells, extensively, the “amount of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions” based on the fixed groups of cells or the fixed groups of group of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for the “Cancer’s Recognition” in terms of these messy and dense SuperHyperModels where embedded notions are illustrated?*

It's motivation to find notions to use in this dense model is titled “SuperHyperGraphs”. Thus it motivates us to define different types of “SuperHyperStable-Decompositions” and “Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions” on “SuperHyperGraph” and “Extreme SuperHyperGraph”. Then the research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and to find some connections amid this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to get some instances and examples to make clarifications about the framework of this research. The general results and some results about some connections are some avenues to make key point of this research, “Cancer’s Recognition”, more understandable and more clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. In the beginning, I introduce basic definitions to clarify about preliminaries. In the subsection “Preliminaries”, initial definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are deeply-introduced and in-depth-discussed. The elementary concepts are clarified and illustrated completely and sometimes review literature are applied to make sense about what's going to figure out about the upcoming sections. The main definitions and their clarifications alongside some results about new notions, SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, are figured out in sections “SuperHyperStable-Decompositions” and “Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions”. In the sense of tackling on getting results and in Stable-Decompositions to make sense about continuing the research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Extreme SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, corresponded SuperHyperClasses are figured out to debut what's done in this section, titled “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. As going back to origin of the notions, there are some smart steps toward the common notions to extend the new notions in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph, in the sections “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. The starter research about the general SuperHyperRelations and as concluding and closing section of theoretical research are contained in the section “General Results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and they are well-known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions as elicited and discussed in the sections, “General Results”, “SuperHyperStable-Decompositions”, “Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what's done about the SuperHyperNotions to make sense about excellency of this research and going to figure out the word “best” as the description and adjective for this research as presented in section, “SuperHyperStable-Decompositions”. The keyword of this research debut in the section “Applications in Cancer’s Recognition” with two cases and subsections “Case 1: The Initial Steps Toward SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: The Increasing Steps Toward SuperHyperMultipartite as SuperHyperModel”. In the section, “Open Problems”, there are some scrutiny and discernment on what's done and what's

happened in this research in the terms of “questions” and “problems” to make sense to figure out this research in featured style. The advantages and the limitations of this research alongside about what’s done in this research to make sense and to get sense about what’s figured out are included in the section, “Conclusion and Closing Remarks”.

3 Extreme Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [131],Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [131],Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [131],Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [131],Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](Ref. [131], Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [131],Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (Ref. [131],Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (Ref. [131],Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to Ref. [131].

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [131],Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Stable-Decompositions of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$^-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]-0, 1^+[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [131],Definition 2.2,p.2).

Let X be a Stable-Decompositions of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\begin{aligned} T_A(X) &= \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}, \\ I_A(X) &= \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}, \\ \text{and } F_A(X) &= \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [131], Definition 2.5,p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.6 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [131], Definition 2.7,p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;

- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 401
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 402
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 403
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- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 405
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- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 407
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If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG). 409
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Definition 3.7 (t-norm). (Ref. [131], Definition 2.7, p.3). 411

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$: 412
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- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$; 414
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$; 415
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$; 416
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$. 417

Definition 3.8. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.9. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.10. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). 418

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where 419
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- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ; 421
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 422
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- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ; 424
425
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 426
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- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 428
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 429

$$(vii) \sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V, (i = 1, 2, \dots, n);$$

$$(viii) \sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V, (i' = 1, 2, \dots, n').$$

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.11 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [131], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.12. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;

- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Definition 3.14. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$.

Definition 3.15. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**;
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**;
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**;
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**.

Definition 3.16 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). (Ref. [131], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$.

Definition 3.17 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [131], Definition 5.4, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

Definition 3.18. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a \text{ and } E'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a \text{ and } E'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

$$\text{and } |E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a \text{ and } V'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a \text{ and } V'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

Definition 3.19. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable-Decompositions).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme

SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;
- (v) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;
- (vii) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Definition 3.20. ((Extreme/Neutrosophic) δ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then

(i) an δ -**SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$\begin{aligned} |S \cap N(s)| &> |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta; \\ |S \cap N(s)| &< |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperDefensive**;

(ii) a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions such that either of the following Neutrosophic expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$\begin{aligned} |S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} &> |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta; \\ |S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} &< |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive**.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, there's a need to “**redefine**” the notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.21. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable.

Definition 3.22. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2)

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.22)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions more Neutrosophicly understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.23. Assume a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if the Table (3) holds.

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

4 Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 4.1. (Extreme event).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Any Extreme k -subset of A of V is called **Extreme k -event** and if $k = 2$, then Extreme subset of A of V is called **Extreme event**. The following expression is called **Extreme probability** of A .

$$E(A) = \sum_{a \in A} E(a). \quad (4.1)$$

Definition 4.2. (Extreme Independent).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. s Extreme k -events $A_i, i \in I$ is called **Extreme s -independent** if the following expression is called **Extreme s -independent criteria**

$$E(\cap_{i \in I} A_i) = \prod_{i \in I} P(A_i).$$

And if $s = 2$, then Extreme k -events of A and B is called **Extreme independent**. The following expression is called **Extreme independent criteria**

$$E(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (4.2)$$

Definition 4.3. (Extreme Variable).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Any k -function Stable-Decompositions like E is called **Extreme k -Variable**. If $k = 2$, then any 2-function Stable-Decompositions like E is called **Extreme Variable**.

The notion of independent on Extreme Variable is likewise.

Definition 4.4. (Extreme Expectation).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. A Extreme k -Variable E has a number is called **Extreme Expectation** if the following expression is called **Extreme Expectation criteria**

$$Ex(E) = \sum_{\alpha \in V} E(\alpha)P(\alpha).$$

Definition 4.5. (Extreme Crossing).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. A Extreme number is called **Extreme Crossing** if the following expression is called **Extreme Crossing criteria**

$$Cr(S) = \min\{\text{Number of Crossing in a Plane Embedding of } S\}.$$

Lemma 4.6. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let m and n propose special Stable-Decompositions. Then with $m \geq 4n$,

Proof. Consider a planar embedding G of G with $cr(G)$ crossings. Let S be a Extreme random k -subset of V obtained by choosing each SuperHyperVertex of G Extreme independently with probability Stable-Decompositions $p := 4n/m$, and set $H := G[S]$ and $H := G[S]$.

Define random variables X, Y, Z on V as follows: X is the Extreme number of SuperHyperVertices, Y the Extreme number of SuperHyperEdges, and Z the Extreme number of crossings of H . The trivial bound noted above, when applied to H , yields the inequality $Z \geq cr(H) \geq Y - 3X$. By linearity of Extreme Expectation,

$$E(Z) \geq E(Y) - 3E(X).$$

Now $E(X) = pn$, $E(Y) = p^2m$ (each SuperHyperEdge having some SuperHyperEnds) and $E(Z) = p^4cr(G)$ (each crossing being defined by some SuperHyperVertices). Hence

$$p^4cr(G) \geq p^2m - 3pn.$$

Dividing both sides by p^4 , we have:

$$cr(G) \geq \frac{pm - 3n}{p^3} = \frac{n}{(4n/m)^3} = \frac{1}{64}m^3n^2.$$

□

Theorem 4.7. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let l be the Extreme number of SuperHyperLines in the plane passing through at least $k + 1$ of these points, where $1 \leq k \leq 2\sqrt{2n}$. Then $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

Proof. Form a Extreme SuperHyperGraph G with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdge are the segments between conseDecompositionive points on the SuperHyperLines which pass through at least $k + 1$ points of P . This Extreme SuperHyperGraph has at least kl SuperHyperEdges and Extreme crossing at most l choose two. Thus either $kl < 4n$, in which case $l < 4n/k \leq 32n^2/k^3$, or $l^2/2 > 1$ choose $2 \geq cr(G) \geq (kl)^3/64n^2$ by the Extreme Crossing Lemma, and again $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

□

Theorem 4.8. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let k be the number of pairs of points of P at unit SuperHyperDistance. Then $k < 5n^{4/3}$.

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Draw a SuperHyperUnit SuperHyperCircle around each SuperHyperPoint of P . Let n_i be the Extreme number of these SuperHyperCircles passing through exactly i points of P . Then $\sum i = 0^{n-1}n_i = n$ and $k = \frac{1}{2} \sum i = 0^{n-1}in_i$. Now form a Extreme SuperHyperGraph H with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdges are the SuperHyperArcs between conseDecompositionive SuperHyperPoints on the SuperHyperCircles that pass through at least three SuperHyperPoints of P . Then

$$e(H) = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} in_i = 2k - n_1 - 2n_2 \geq 2k - 2n.$$

Some SuperHyperPairs of SuperHyperVertices of H might be joined by some parallel SuperHyperEdges. Delete from H one of each SuperHyperPair of parallel SuperHyperEdges, so as to obtain a simple Extreme SuperHyperGraph G with

$e(G) \geq k - n$. Now $cr(G) \leq n(n - 1)$ because G is formed from at most n SuperHyperCircles, and any two SuperHyperCircles cross at most twice. Thus either $e(G) < 4n$, in which case $k < 5n < 5n^{4/3}$, or $n^2 > n(n - 1) \geq cr(G) \geq (k - n)^3 / 64n^2$ by the Extreme Crossing Lemma, and $k < 4n^{4/3} + n < 5n^{4/3}$. $\square$

Proposition 4.9. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let X be a nonnegative Extreme Variable and t a positive real number. Then*

$$P(X \geq t) \leq \frac{E(X)}{t}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} E(X) &= \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V\} \geq \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= \sum \{tP(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} = t \sum \{P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= tP(X \geq t). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the first and last members by t yields the asserted inequality. $\square$

Corollary 4.10. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let X_n be a nonnegative integer-valued variable in a probability Stable-Decompositions $(V_n, E_n), n \geq 1$. If $E(X_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $P(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.*

Proof.

Theorem 4.11. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most $\lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$.*

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ is up. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ and let S be a given SuperHyperSet of $k + 1$ SuperHyperVertices of G , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The probability that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G is $(1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}$, this being the probability that none of the $\binom{k+1}{2}$ pairs of SuperHyperVertices of S is a SuperHyperEdge of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph G .

Let A_S denote the event that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G , and let X_S denote the indicator Extreme Variable for this Extreme Event. By equation, we have

$$E(X_S) = P(X_S = 1) = P(A_S) = (1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

Let X be the number of stable SuperHyperSets of cardinality $k + 1$ in G . Then

$$X = \sum \{X_S : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\}$$

and so, by those,

$$E(X) = \sum \{E(X_S) : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\} = \binom{n}{k+1} (1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

We bound the right-hand side by invoking two elementary inequalities:

$$\binom{n}{k+1} \leq \frac{n^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \text{ and } 1 - p \leq e^{-p}.$$

This yields the following upper bound on $E(X)$. 781

$$E(X) \leq \frac{n^{k+1} e^{-p(k+1)\text{choose}2}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{ne^{-pk/2k+1}}{(k+1)!}$$

Suppose now that $k = \lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$. Then $k \geq 2p^{-1} \log n$, so $ne^{-pk/2} \leq 1$. Because k grows at least as fast as the logarithm of n , implies that $E(X) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Because X is integer-valued and nonnegative, we deduce from Corollary that $P(X = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, a Extreme SuperHyperGraph in $\mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most k . 782
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786 $\square$

Definition 4.12. (Extreme Variance). 787

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. A Extreme k -Variable E has a number is called **Extreme Variance** if the following expression is called **Extreme Variance criteria** 788
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$$Vx(E) = Ex((X - Ex(X))^2).$$

Theorem 4.13. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let X be a Extreme Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then 792
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$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) \leq \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let X be a Extreme Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then 795
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$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) = E((X - Ex(X))^2 \geq t^2) \leq \frac{Ex((X - Ex(X))^2)}{t^2} = \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

$\square$ 798

Corollary 4.14. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let X_n be a Extreme Variable in a probability Stable-Decompositions (V_n, E_n) , $n \geq 1$. If $Ex(X_n) \neq 0$ and $V(X_n) \ll E^2(X_n)$, then 799
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$$E(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Set $X := X_n$ and $t := |Ex(X_n)|$ in Chebyshev's Inequality, and observe that $E(X_n = 0) \leq E(|X_n - Ex(X_n)| \geq |Ex(X_n)|)$ because $|X_n - Ex(X_n)| = |Ex(X_n)|$ when $X_n = 0$. 803
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806 $\square$

Theorem 4.15. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$. For $0 \leq k \leq n$, set $f(k) := (n \text{ choose } k)2^{-(k \text{ choose } 2)}$ and let k^* be the least value of k for which $f(k)$ is less than one. Then almost surely $\alpha(G)$ takes one of the three values $k^* - 2, k^* - 1, k^*$. 807
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Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. As in the proof of related Theorem, the result is straightforward. 812
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814 $\square$

Corollary 4.16. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$ and let f and k^* be as defined in previous Theorem. Then either:

(i). $f(k^*) \ll 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 2$ or $k^* - 1$,
or

(ii). $f(k^* - 1) \gg 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 1$ or k^* .

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Definition 4.17. (Extreme Threshold).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let P be a monotone property of SuperHyperGraphs (one which is preserved when SuperHyperEdges are added). Then a **Extreme Threshold** for P is a function $f(n)$ such that:

(i). if $p \ll f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely does not have P ,

(ii). if $p \gg f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has P .

Definition 4.18. (Extreme Balanced).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let F be a fixed Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then there is a threshold function for the property of containing a copy of F as a Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph is called **Extreme Balanced**.

Theorem 4.19. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let F be a nonempty balanced Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph with k SuperHyperVertices and l SuperHyperEdges. Then $n^{-k/l}$ is a threshold function for the property of containing F as a Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph.

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 4.20. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{E_i\}_{i=1}^4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,4}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,4}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

Figure 1. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_i\}_{i=1}^4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,4}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,4}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_i\}_{i=1}^4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,3}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 3. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 4. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 868
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_4, E_3, E_2\}, \{E_5, E_3, E_2\}, \{E_1, E_3\}, \{E_i\}\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i, V_j\}_{V_i \in \{V_1, V_2, N, F\}, V_j \in \{V_4, O, H\}}, \\
 & \{V_3, O\}, \{V_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 871
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_a, V_b, V_c, V_d\}_{a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}, b \in \{6, 7, 8\}, c \in \{9, 10, 11, 12\}, d \in \{13, 14, 15\}, \{V_i\}}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 875
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Figure 5. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{ E_{2i+1, i=0^4}, E_{2j+23, i=0^4} \} \\
 & \quad \{ E_{2i+2, i=0^4}, E_{2j+23, i=0^4} \}, \{ E_{ab+c, b \geq 3} \}, \{ E_i \} \}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^4. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{ V_{2i+1, i=0^4}, V_{2j+23, i=0^4} \} \\
 & \quad \{ V_{2i+2, i=0^4}, V_{2j+23, i=0^4} \}, \{ V_{ab+c, b \geq 3} \}, \{ V_i \} \}. \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 6. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &\{ \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}\}, \\
 &\{E_{ab+c_{a,b \geq 3}}\}, \{E_i\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &\{V_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}\}, \\
 &\{V_{ab+c_{a,b \geq 3}}\}, \{V_i\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 7. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{ \{E_1, E_2, E_3\}, \{E_i, E_j\}_{i,j \in \{1,2,3\}}, \{E_a\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{ \{V_a, V_b, V_c\}_{a \in \{1,2,3\}, b \in \{4,5,6,7\}, c \in \{8,9,10,11\}}, \\
 &= \{V_d, V_e\}_{V_d \in E_i, V_e \in E_j, i \neq j, i, j \neq 4}, \{V_f\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{ \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}, E_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+2_{i=0^4}}, E_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\}, \{E_{a+b+c_a, b \geq 3}\}, \{E_i\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{ \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}, V_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\} \\
 &= \{V_{2i+2_{i=0^4}}, V_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\}, \{V_{a+b+c_a, b \geq 3}\}, \{V_i\} \}. \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 8. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 891
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893
894

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 & \{ \{E_1, E_2, E_3\}, \{E_i, E_j\}_{i,j \in \{1,2,3\}}, \{E_a\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 & \{ \{V_a, V_b, V_c\}_{a \in \{1,2,3\}, b \in \{4,5,6,7\}, c \in \{8,9,10,11\}}, \\
 & \{V_d, V_e\}_{V_d \in E_i, V_e \in E_j, i \neq j, i, j \neq 4}, \{V_f\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 895
896
897

Figure 9. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 10. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 11. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{E_6, E_7, E_8\}, \{E_i, E_j\}_{i,j \in \{6,7,8\}}, \{E_k\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{V_1, V_{6(4)}\}, \{V_2, V_{6(5)}\}, \{V_3, V_{5(4)}\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{E_i\}_{i=2,3,4,5,6}\}, \\
 A &\subseteq \{E_i\}_{i=2,3,4,5,6}, \{E_i\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^2. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{V_a\}_{a=4,5,6,9,10}, \\
 A &\subseteq \{V_a\}_{a=2,3,4,5,6}, \{V_b\}_{b=1,2,3,7,8}, \\
 A &\subseteq \{V_a\}_{b=1,2,3,7,8}, \{V_c\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 12. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 903
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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{E_6, E_7, E_8\}, \{E_i, E_j\}_{i,j \in \{6,7,8\}}, \{E_k\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{V_1, V_{6(4)}\}, \{V_2, V_{6(5)}\}, \{V_3, V_{5(4)}\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 907
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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{E_i\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{V_2, V_3\}, \{V_a\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 13. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 911
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0}^2}\}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1_{i=0}^2}\}, \{E_j\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_{2i+2_{i=0}^1}, V_5\}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{V_{2i+2_{i=0}^1}, V_5\}, \{V_a\}\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 915
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Figure 14. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 15. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 16. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

918

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, \{E_j\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{V_1, V_3, V_{10}, V_{22}\}, \dots\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= az^b.$$

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- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, \{E_j\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{V_{27}, V_2, V_{10}, V_{22}\}, \dots\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= az^b.$$

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- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 17. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, \{E_j\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{V_{27}, V_2, V_{10}, V_{22}\}, \dots\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= az^b.$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{E_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}, \{E_i\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{V_{E_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}}\}, B \subseteq \{V_{E_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}}, \{V_a\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^3.$$

Figure 18. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 19. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 20. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 932
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{E_i\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{\text{INTERNAL SuperHyperVERTICES}\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = az^b. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 935
936
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{E_i\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{V_i\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = z. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 21. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{E_{2i+2_{i=01}}\}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+2_{i=01}}\}, \{E_i\} \}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^2. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{V_a, V_b, V_c, V_d\} \\
 & \quad \} V_a \in \{R, P, M, J, V_1\}, V_b \in \{H_6, O_6, E_6, C_6\}, V_c \in \{S_6, R_6, T_6, V_7, V_8, V_9\}, V_d \in \{T_3, S_3, U_3, V_4, V_5\} \}, \\
 & \quad \{V_a\} \}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 4.21. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded

Figure 22. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Proposition 4.22. *Assume a connected non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices in an Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions, minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.*

Proposition 4.23. *Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme SuperHyperVertices, then the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions is at least*

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions is at least the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Extreme Stable-Decompositions in some cases but the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices, has the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions.

Proposition 4.24. *Assume a simple Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then the Extreme number of type-result-R-Stable-Decompositions has, the least Extreme cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for Extreme cardinality, is the Extreme*

cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_{E'}, c_{E''}, c_{E'''}\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

If there's a Extreme type-result-R-Stable-Decompositions with the least Extreme cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for cardinality. 967
968

Proposition 4.25. Assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally, 969
970

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions}} = \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

Is a Extreme type-result-Stable-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Extreme type-result-Stable-Decompositions is the cardinality of 971
972
973

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions}} = \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

Proof. Assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The SuperHyperSet of the SuperHyperVertices $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ isn't a quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions since neither amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges nor amount of SuperHyperVertices where amount refers to the Extreme number of SuperHyperVertices(-/SuperHyperEdges) more than one to form any kind of SuperHyperEdges or any number of SuperHyperEdges. Let us consider the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E,E'=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

This Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices has the eligibilities to propose property such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices but the maximum Extreme cardinality indicates that these Extreme type-SuperHyperSets couldn't give us the Extreme lower bound in the term of Extreme sharpness. In other words, the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E,E'=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices implies at least on-quasi-triangle style is up but sometimes the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E,E'=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices is free-quasi-triangle and it doesn't make a contradiction to the supposition on the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus the minimum case never happens in the generality of the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraphs. Thus if we assume in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is a quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Then we've lost some connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperClasses of the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraphs titled free-triangle, on-triangle, and their quasi-types but the SuperHyperStable is only up in this quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions. It's the contradiction to that fact on the generality. There are some counterexamples to deny this statement. One of them comes from the setting of the graph titled path and cycle as the counterexamples-classes or reversely direction star as the examples-classes, are well-known classes in that setting and they could be considered as the examples-classes and counterexamples-classes for the tight bound of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Let $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ in mind. There's no necessity on the SuperHyperEdge since we need at least two SuperHyperVertices to form a SuperHyperEdge. It doesn't withdraw the principles of the main definition since there's no condition to be satisfied but the condition is on the existence of the SuperHyperEdge instead of acting on the SuperHyperVertices. In other words, if there's a SuperHyperEdge, then the Extreme SuperHyperSet has the necessary condition for the intended definition to be applied. Thus the $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ is withdrawn not by the conditions of the main definition but by the necessity of the pre-condition on the usage of the main definition.

The Extreme structure of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions decorates the Extreme SuperHyperVertices don't have received any Extreme connections so as this Extreme style implies different versions of Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum Extreme cardinality in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are spotlight. The lower Extreme bound is to have the maximum Extreme groups of Extreme SuperHyperVertices have perfect Extreme connections inside each of SuperHyperEdges and the outside of this Extreme SuperHyperSet doesn't matter but regarding the connectedness of the used Extreme SuperHyperGraph arising from its Extreme properties taken from the fact that it's simple. If there's no more than one Extreme SuperHyperVertex in the targeted Extreme SuperHyperSet, then there's no Extreme connection. Furthermore, the Extreme existence of one Extreme SuperHyperVertex has no Extreme effect to talk about the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. Since at least two Extreme SuperHyperVertices involve to make a title in the Extreme background of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The Extreme SuperHyperGraph is obvious if it has no Extreme SuperHyperEdge but at least two Extreme SuperHyperVertices make the Extreme version of Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the Extreme setting of non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph, there are at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge. It's necessary to mention that the word "Simple" is used as Extreme adjective for the initial Extreme SuperHyperGraph, induces there's no Extreme appearance of the loop Extreme version of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge and this Extreme SuperHyperGraph is said to be loopless. The Extreme adjective "loop" on the basic Extreme framework engages one Extreme SuperHyperVertex but it never happens in this Extreme setting. With these Extreme bases, on a Extreme SuperHyperGraph, there's at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge thus there's at least a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions has the Extreme cardinality of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus, a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions has the Extreme cardinality at least a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$. This Extreme SuperHyperSet isn't a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions since either the Extreme SuperHyperGraph is an obvious Extreme SuperHyperModel thus it never happens since

there's no Extreme usage of this Extreme framework and even more there's no Extreme connection inside or the Extreme SuperHyperGraph isn't obvious and as its consequences, there's a Extreme contradiction with the term "Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions" since the maximum Extreme cardinality never happens for this Extreme style of the Extreme SuperHyperSet and beyond that there's no Extreme connection inside as mentioned in first Extreme case in the forms of drawback for this selected Extreme SuperHyperSet. Let

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Comes up. This Extreme case implies having the Extreme style of on-quasi-triangle Extreme style on the every Extreme elements of this Extreme SuperHyperSet. Precisely, the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions is the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that some Extreme amount of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are on-quasi-triangle Extreme style. The Extreme cardinality of the v SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Is the maximum in comparison to the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

But the lower Extreme bound is up. Thus the minimum Extreme cardinality of the maximum Extreme cardinality ends up the Extreme discussion. The first Extreme term refers to the Extreme setting of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph but this key point is enough since there's a Extreme SuperHyperClass of a Extreme SuperHyperGraph has no on-quasi-triangle Extreme style amid some amount of its Extreme SuperHyperVertices. This Extreme setting of the Extreme SuperHyperModel proposes a Extreme SuperHyperSet has only some amount Extreme SuperHyperVertices from one Extreme SuperHyperEdge such that there's no Extreme amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges more than one involving these some amount of these Extreme SuperHyperVertices. The Extreme cardinality of this Extreme SuperHyperSet is the maximum and the Extreme case is occurred in the minimum Extreme situation. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Has the maximum Extreme cardinality such that

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Contains some Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct-covers-order-amount Extreme SuperHyperEdges for amount of Extreme SuperHyperVertices taken from the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

It means that the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions for the Extreme SuperHyperGraph as used Extreme background in the Extreme terms of worst Extreme case and the common

theme of the lower Extreme bound occurred in the specific Extreme SuperHyperClasses of the Extreme SuperHyperGraphs which are Extreme free-quasi-triangle. 984

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme number of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Then every Extreme SuperHyperVertex has at least no Extreme SuperHyperEdge with others in common. Thus those Extreme SuperHyperVertices have the eligibles to be contained in a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. Those Extreme SuperHyperVertices are potentially included in a Extreme style-R-Stable-Decompositions. Formally, consider 985

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

Are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z.$$

where the $\sim$ isn't an equivalence relation but only the symmetric relation on the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The formal definition is as follows.

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z$$

if and only if Z_i and Z_j are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices and there's only and only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ between the Extreme SuperHyperVertices Z_i and Z_j . The other definition for the Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ in the terms of Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions is

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}.$$

This definition coincides with the definition of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions but with slightly differences in the maximum Extreme cardinality amid those Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$\max_z \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\} | \text{Extreme cardinality},$$

and

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

is formalized with mathematical literatures on the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. Let $Z_i \overset{E}{\sim} Z_j$, be defined as Z_i and Z_j are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to the Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus,

$$E = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \overset{E}{\sim} Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}.$$

Or

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

But with the slightly differences, 986

Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions =

$$\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid \forall i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z, \exists E_x, Z_i \overset{E_x}{\sim} Z_j\}.$$

Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions = 987

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Thus $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is a Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions where $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is fixed that means $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. for all Extreme intended SuperHyperVertices but in a Extreme Stable-Decompositions, $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ could be different and it's not unique. To sum them up, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme SuperHyperVertices, then the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions is at least the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Extreme Stable-Decompositions in some cases but the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices, has the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions.

The obvious SuperHyperGraph has no Extreme SuperHyperEdges. But the non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperModel is up. The quasi-SuperHyperModel addresses some issues about the Extreme optimal SuperHyperObject. It specially delivers some remarks on the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges for distinct amount of Extreme SuperHyperVertices up to all taken from that Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices but this Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices is either has the maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality or it doesn't have maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality. In a non-obvious SuperHyperModel, there's at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge containing at least all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Thus it forms a Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions where the Extreme completion of the Extreme incidence is up in that. Thus it's, literarily, a Extreme embedded R-Stable-Decompositions. The SuperHyperNotions of embedded SuperHyperSet and quasi-SuperHyperSet coincide. In the original setting, these types of SuperHyperSets only don't satisfy on the maximum SuperHyperCardinality. Thus the embedded setting is elected such that those SuperHyperSets have the maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality and they're Extreme SuperHyperOptimal. The less than two distinct types of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are included in the minimum Extreme style of the embedded Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. The interior types of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are deciders. Since the Extreme number of SuperHyperNeighbors are only affected by the interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices. The common connections, more precise and more formal, the perfect unique connections inside the Extreme SuperHyperSet for any distinct types of Extreme SuperHyperVertices pose the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. Thus Extreme exterior SuperHyperVertices could be used only in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge and in Extreme SuperHyperRelation with the interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices in that Extreme SuperHyperEdge. In the embedded Extreme Stable-Decompositions, there's the usage of exterior Extreme SuperHyperVertices since they've more connections inside more than outside. Thus the title "exterior" is more relevant than the title "interior". One Extreme SuperHyperVertex has no connection, inside. Thus, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices with one SuperHyperElement has been ignored in the exploring to lead on the optimal case implying the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. The Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions with the exclusion of the exclusion of all Extreme SuperHyperVertices in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge and with other terms,

the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions with the inclusion of all Extreme SuperHyperVertices in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, is a Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions. To sum them up, in a connected non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices in an Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions, minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

The main definition of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions has two titles. a Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions and its corresponded quasi-maximum Extreme R-SuperHyperCardinality are two titles in the terms of quasi-R-styles. For any Extreme number, there's a Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions with that quasi-maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality in the terms of the embedded Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If there's an embedded Extreme SuperHyperGraph, then the Extreme quasi-SuperHyperNotions lead us to take the collection of all the Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositionss for all Extreme numbers less than its Extreme corresponded maximum number. The essence of the Extreme Stable-Decompositions ends up but this essence starts up in the terms of the Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions, again and more in the operations of collecting all the Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositionss acted on the all possible used formations of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph to achieve one Extreme number. This Extreme number is

considered as the equivalence class for all corresponded quasi-R-Stable-Decompositionss. Let $z_{\text{Extreme Number}}$, $S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}$ and $G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}$ be a Extreme number, a Extreme SuperHyperSet and a Extreme Stable-Decompositions. Then

$$\begin{aligned} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

As its consequences, the formal definition of the Extreme Stable-Decompositions is re-formalized and redefined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more precise perceptions, the follow-up expressions propose another formal

technical definition for the Extreme Stable-Decompositions. 1063

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid & \\
S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}, & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

In more concise and more convenient ways, the modified definition for the Extreme Stable-Decompositions poses the upcoming expressions. 1064

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

To translate the statement to this mathematical literature, the formulae will be revised. 1065

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

And then, 1066

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

To get more visions in the closer look-up, there's an overall overlook. 1067

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid & \\
S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}, & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid & \\
S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}, & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} & \\
= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the extension of these types of approaches is up. Since the new term, “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood”, could be redefined as the collection of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that any amount of its Extreme SuperHyperVertices are incident to a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. It’s, literarily, another name for “Extreme Quasi-Stable-Decompositions” but, precisely, it’s the generalization of “Extreme Quasi-Stable-Decompositions” since “Extreme Quasi-Stable-Decompositions” happens “Extreme Stable-Decompositions” in a Extreme SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and background but “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood” may not happens “Extreme Stable-Decompositions” in a Extreme SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and preliminarily background since there are some ambiguities about the Extreme SuperHyperCardinality arise from it. To get orderly keywords, the terms, “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood”, “Extreme Quasi-Stable-Decompositions”, and “Extreme Stable-Decompositions” are up.

Thus, let $z_{\text{Extreme Number}}$, $N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}$ and $G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}}$ be a Extreme number, a Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood and a Extreme Stable-Decompositions and the new terms are up.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid & \\
|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

And with go back to initial structure,

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

To make sense with the precise words in the terms of “R-”, the follow-up illustrations are coming up.

The following Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions.

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

The Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is an **Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Extreme type-SuperHyperSet with **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there’s no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge amid some Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by **Extreme Stable-Decompositions** is related to the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

There’s not only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Extreme Stable-Decompositions is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Stable-Decompositions is a Extreme SuperHyperSet **includes** only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex. But the Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

doesn’t have less than two SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet since they’ve come from at least so far an SuperHyperEdge. Thus the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions **is** up. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{xy\}$$

or

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{zy\}$$

is an Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Stable-Decompositions **and** it's an Extreme **Stable-Decompositions**. Since it's **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet $\bar{S}$ of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some amount Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Stable-Decompositions. There isn't only less than two Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus the non-obvious Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is up. The non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Decompositions, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the Extreme SuperHyperSet, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

does includes only less than two SuperHyperVertices in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ but it's impossible in the case, they've corresponded to an SuperHyperEdge. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets called the

Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions,

is only and only

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling. It's also, not only a Extreme free-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel and a Extreme on-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel but also it's a Extreme stable embedded SuperHyperModel. But all only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions amid those obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme Stable-Decompositions, are

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. 1111

To sum them up, assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

To sum them up, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them. 1112 1113 1114 1115 1116 1117

Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Let a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $ESHE : E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has some Extreme SuperHyperVertices r . Consider all Extreme numbers of those Extreme SuperHyperVertices from that Extreme SuperHyperEdge excluding more than r distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices, exclude to any given Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Consider there's a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions with the least cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for Extreme cardinality. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \setminus \{z\}$ is a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely but it isn't a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. Since it doesn't have **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some SuperHyperVertices uniquely. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices but it isn't a Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions. Since it **doesn't do** the Extreme procedure such that such that there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely [there are at least one Extreme SuperHyperVertex outside implying there's, sometimes in the connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$, a Extreme SuperHyperVertex, titled its Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, to that Extreme SuperHyperVertex in the Extreme SuperHyperSet S so as S doesn't do "the Extreme procedure"]. There's only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex **outside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet, $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$, in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood. Thus the obvious Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions, V_{ESHE} is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions, V_{ESHE} , **is** a Extreme SuperHyperSet, V_{ESHE} , **includes** only **all** Extreme SuperHyperVertices does forms any kind of Extreme pairs are titled Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices V_{ESHE} , is the **maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices **such that** there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely. Thus, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Any Extreme R-Stable-Decompositions only contains all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices and all exterior Extreme SuperHyperVertices from the unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge where 1118 1119 1120 1121 1122 1123 1124 1125 1126 1127 1128 1129 1130 1131 1132 1133 1134 1135 1136 1137 1138 1139 1140 1141 1142 1143 1144 1145 1146 1147 1148 1149 1150 1151 1152 1153

there's any of them has all possible Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors in and there's all Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhods in with no exception minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to some of them not all of them but everything is possible about Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhods and Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors out. 1154
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The SuperHyperNotion, namely, Stable-Decompositions, is up. There's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. The following Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Decompositions. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices], 1158
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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Decompositions. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices], 1163
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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is an **Extreme Stable-Decompositions** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Extreme type-SuperHyperSet with **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. There are not only **two** Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Extreme Stable-Decompositions is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Stable-Decompositions is a Extreme SuperHyperSet **includes** only **two** Extreme SuperHyperVertices. But the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices], 1165
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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Doesn't have less than three SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the 1176
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Extreme Stable-Decompositions **is** up. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Decompositions. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is an Extreme Stable-Decompositions $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some Extreme SuperHyperVertices given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Stable-Decompositions **and** it's an Extreme **Stable-Decompositions**. Since it's **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. There aren't only less than three Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Thus the non-obvious Extreme Stable-Decompositions,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Decompositions, not:

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the Extreme SuperHyperSet, not:

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Does includes only less than three SuperHyperVertices in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the

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“Extreme Stable-Decompositions”

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amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets called the

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Extreme Stable-Decompositions,

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is only and only

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. □

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5 The Extreme Departures on The Theoretical Results Toward Theoretical Motivations

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The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses.

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Proposition 5.1. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then 1209

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{ E_{2i+1} \}_{i=1}^{\lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor} \}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{ E_{2i+1} \}_{i=1}^{\lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor}, \{ E_i \}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{ V_{2i+1}^{\text{INTERNAL}} \}_{i=1}^{\lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor} \}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{ V_{2i+1}^{\text{INTERNAL}} \}_{i=1}^{\lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor}, \{ V_a \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$
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Proof. Let 1212

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}
 \end{aligned}$$
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}, V_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. 1214
There's a new way to redefine as 1215

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{ V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 1216
corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1217
The latter is straightforward. □ 1218

Example 5.2. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath 1219
 $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the 1220
Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1221

Proposition 5.3. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. 1222

Figure 23. a Extreme SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Example (16.5)

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_{2i+1} \mid 2i+1 = \lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor\}\}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1} \mid 2i+1 = \lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor, \{E_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_{2i+1}^{INTERNAL} \mid 2i+1 = \lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor\}\}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{V_{2i+1}^{INTERNAL} \mid 2i+1 = \lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor, \{V_a\}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{\frac{\lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{\lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 24. a Extreme SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.7)

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{|ESHG|}, V_{|ESHG|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 5.4. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

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Proposition 5.5. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then 1237

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{\{E_i\}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= z. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{\{V_i^{\text{INTERNAL}}\}, A \subseteq \{V_i^{\text{INTERNAL}}\}, \{V^{\text{INTERNAL}}\}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= z^3.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1238

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
\text{CENTER}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

1239

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
E_2, \text{CENTER}
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's 1240
a new way to redefine as 1241

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 1242
corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1243
The latter is straightforward. □ 1244

Example 5.6. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar 1245
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by 1246
the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the 1247
connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel 1248
(25), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1249

Proposition 5.7. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. 1250

Figure 25. a Extreme SuperHyperStar Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.9)

Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges\}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges\}, \\
 & \{E_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices\}, \\
 & B \subseteq \{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices\}, \\
 & \{V_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.
 The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one
 SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the
 SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Decompositions could be applied.
 There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one
 SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions taken from a connected Extreme
 SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only
 minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.8. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme
 SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured.
 The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme
 result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
 SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the
 Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

Proposition 5.9. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
\cdots, \\
E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Decompositions could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 5.10. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

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Proposition 5.11. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$.

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Figure 27. a Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Example (16.13)

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_{2i+1}^{*2i+1} = \lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor\}\}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1}^{*2i+1} = \lfloor |E_{NSHG}^*| \rfloor, \{E_i^*\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_{2i+1}^{INTERNAL2i+1} = \lfloor |E_{NSHG}^*| \rfloor\}\}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{V_{2i+1}^{INTERNAL2i+1} = \lfloor |E_{NSHG}^*| \rfloor, \{V_a\}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 & CENTER, E_2^*
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2^*, CENTER
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 28. a Extreme SuperHyperWheel Extreme Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.15)

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Decompositions could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperStable-Decompositions proposes some longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.12. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

6 The Surveys of Mathematical Sets On The Results But As The Initial Motivation

For the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, some general results are introduced.

Remark 6.1. Let remind that the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is “redefined” on the positions of the alphabets.

Corollary 6.2. Assume Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Extreme SuperHyperStable – Decompositions} = \\ & \{ \text{the SuperHyperStable – Decomposition of the SuperHyperVertices} \mid \\ & \max | \text{SuperHyperOffensive} \\ & \text{SuperHyperStable – Decompositions} \\ & | \text{Extremecardinalityamidthose SuperHyperStable – Decompositions.} \} \end{aligned}$$

plus one Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to one. Where σ_i is the unary operation on the SuperHyperVertices of the SuperHyperGraph to assign the determinacy, the indeterminacy and the neutrality, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, respectively.

Corollary 6.3. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph* on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then the notion of *Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* and *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* coincide. 1329
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Corollary 6.4. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph* on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a *conseDecompositionisive* sequence of the *SuperHyperVertices* is a *Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* if and only if it's a *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions*. 1332
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Corollary 6.5. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph* on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a *conseDecompositionisive* sequence of the *SuperHyperVertices* is a *strongest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* if and only if it's a *longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions*. 1336
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Corollary 6.6. Assume *SuperHyperClasses* of a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph* on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* is its *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* and reversely. 1340
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Corollary 6.7. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel)* on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* is its *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* and reversely. 1343
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Corollary 6.8. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* isn't well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* isn't well-defined. 1348
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Corollary 6.9. Assume *SuperHyperClasses* of a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* isn't well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* isn't well-defined. 1351
1352
1353

Corollary 6.10. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel)*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* isn't well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* isn't well-defined. 1354
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Corollary 6.11. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* is well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* is well-defined. 1359
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Corollary 6.12. Assume *SuperHyperClasses* of a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* is well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* is well-defined. 1362
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Corollary 6.13. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel)*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* is well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions* is well-defined. 1365
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Proposition 6.14. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then V is 1370
(i) : the dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions*; 1371
(ii) : the strong dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions*; 1372

(iii) : the connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1373

(iv) : the δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1374

(v) : the strong δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1375

(vi) : the connected δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1376

Proposition 6.15. Let $NTG : (V, E, \sigma, \mu)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then $\emptyset$ is 1377

(i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1378

(ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1379

(iii) : the connected defensive SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1380

(iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1381

(v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1382

(vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1383

Proposition 6.16. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then an independent SuperHyperSet is 1384
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(i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1386

(ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1387

(iii) : the connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1388

(iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1389

(v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1390

(vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1391

Proposition 6.17. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath. Then V is a maximal 1392
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(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1395

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1396

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1397

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1398

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1399

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1400

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1401

Proposition 6.18. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperWheel. Then V is a maximal 1402
1403

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1404

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1405

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1406

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1407

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1408

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1409
1410

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1411

Proposition 6.19. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath. Then the number of 1412
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(i) : the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1415

(ii) : the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1416

(iii) : the connected SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1417

(iv) : the $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1418

(v) : the strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1419

(vi) : the connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1420

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1421
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Proposition 6.20. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperWheel. Then the number of 1423
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(i) : the dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1425

(ii) : the dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1426

(iii) : the dual connected SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1427

(iv) : the dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1428

(v) : the strong dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1429

(vi) : the connected dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1430

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1431
1432

Proposition 6.21. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices is a 1433
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(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1438

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1439

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1440

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1441

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1442

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1443
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Proposition 6.22. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices in the biggest SuperHyperPart is a 1445
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(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1451

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1452

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1453

(iv) : δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1454

(v) : strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1455

(vi) : connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1456

Proposition 6.23. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then Then the number of 1457
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(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1461

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1462

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1463

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1464

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1465

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1466
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is one and it's only S , a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices. Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1468
1469
1470
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Proposition 6.24. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The number of connected component is $|V - S|$ if there's a SuperHyperSet which is a dual 1472
1473

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1474

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1475

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1476

(iv) : SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1477

(v) : strong 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1478

(vi) : connected 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1479

Proposition 6.25. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then the number is at most $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ and the Extreme number is at most $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG)$. 1480
1481

Proposition 6.26. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Extreme number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E)) \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of dual 1482
1483
1484

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1485

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1486

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1487

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1488

(v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1489
1490

(vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1491
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Proposition 6.27. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is $\emptyset$. The number is 0 and the Extreme number is 0, for an independent SuperHyperSet in the setting of dual 1493
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1495

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1496

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1497

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1498

(iv) : 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1499

(v) : strong 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1500

(vi) : connected 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1501

Proposition 6.28. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. Then there's no independent SuperHyperSet. 1502
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Proposition 6.29. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath/SuperHyperWheel. The number is $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ and the Extreme number is $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG : (V, E))$, in the setting of a dual 1504
1505
1506
1507

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1508

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1509

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1510

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1511

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1512
1513

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1514
1515

Proposition 6.30. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStar/complete SuperHyperBipartite/complete SuperHyperMultiPartite. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Extreme number is $\min_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \sum_{t > \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2}} \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of a dual

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1520

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1521

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1522

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1523

(v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1524
1525

(vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1526
1527

Proposition 6.31. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a SuperHyperFamily of the $ESHGs : (V, E)$ Extreme SuperHyperGraphs which are from one-type SuperHyperClass which the result is obtained for the individuals. Then the results also hold for the SuperHyperFamily $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ of these specific SuperHyperClasses of the Extreme SuperHyperGraphs. 1528
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Proposition 6.32. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then $\forall v \in V \setminus S, \exists x \in S$ such that 1532
1533
1534

(i) $v \in N_s(x)$; 1535

(ii) $vx \in E$. 1536

Proposition 6.33. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then 1537
1538

(i) S is SuperHyperStable-Decompositions set; 1539

(ii) there's $S \subseteq S'$ such that $|S'|$ is SuperHyperChromatic number. 1540

Proposition 6.34. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then 1541

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O}$; 1542

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n$. 1543

Proposition 6.35. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is connected. Then 1544
1545

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O} - 1$; 1546

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n - \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(x)$. 1547

Proposition 6.36. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperPath. Then 1548

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1549
1550

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1551

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1552

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only a dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1553
1554

Proposition 6.37. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperPath. Then 1555

(i) the set $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1556
1557

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1558
1559

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1560

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1561
1562

Proposition 6.38. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Then 1563
1564

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1565
1566

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1567
1568

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sigma(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sigma(s)\}$; 1569

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1570
1571

Proposition 6.39. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Then 1572
1573

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1574
1575

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1576

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1577

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1578
1579

Proposition 6.40. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperStar. Then 1580

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c\}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1581

(ii) $\Gamma = 1$; 1582

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(c)$; 1583

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1584
1585

Proposition 6.41. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperWheel. Then 1586

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1587
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(ii) $\Gamma = |\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}|$; 1589

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \Sigma_{\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s);$ 1590

(iv) *the SuperHyperSet $\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1591
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Proposition 6.42. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an odd SuperHyperComplete. Then* 1593

(i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1594
1595

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1;$ 1596

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\Sigma_{s \in S} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}};$ 1597

(iv) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is only a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1598
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Proposition 6.43. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an even SuperHyperComplete. Then* 1600

(i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1601
1602

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor;$ 1603

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\Sigma_{s \in S} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}};$ 1604

(iv) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1605
1606

Proposition 6.44. *Let NSHF : (V, E) be a m-SuperHyperFamily of Extreme SuperHyperStars with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then* 1607
1608

(i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for NSHF;* 1609
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(ii) $\Gamma = m$ for NSHF : (V, E); 1611

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \Sigma_{i=1}^m \Sigma_{j=1}^3 \sigma_j(c_i)$ for NSHF : (V, E); 1612

(iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for NSHF : (V, E).* 1613
1614

Proposition 6.45. *Let NSHF : (V, E) be an m-SuperHyperFamily of odd SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then* 1615
1616
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(i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for NSHF;* 1618
1619

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ for NSHF : (V, E); 1620

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\Sigma_{s \in S} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$ for NSHF : (V, E); 1621

(iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ are only a dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for NSHF : (V, E).* 1622
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Proposition 6.46. *Let NSHF : (V, E) be a m-SuperHyperFamily of even SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then* 1624
1625
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- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1627
1628
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1629
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1630
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ are only dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1631
1632

Proposition 6.47. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1633
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- (i) if $s \geq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then S is an s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1635
1636
1637
- (ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1638
1639
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Proposition 6.48. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1641
1642

- (i) if $s \geq t + 2$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then S is an s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1643
1644
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- (ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1646
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Proposition 6.49. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1649
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- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1652
1653
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1654
1655
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1656
1657
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1658
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Proposition 6.50. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1660
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1662

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1663
1664
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1665
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(iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1667
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(iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1669
1670

Proposition 6.51. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V]$ -SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1671
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(i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1674
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(ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1676
1677

(iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1678
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(iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1680
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Proposition 6.52. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V]$ -SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1682
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(i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1685
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(ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1687
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(iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1689
1690

(iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1691
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Proposition 6.53. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V]$ -SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Then following statements hold; 1693
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(i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1696
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(ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1698
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(iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1700
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(iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1702
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Proposition 6.54. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V]$ -SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Then following statements hold; 1704
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(i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2 -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1707
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- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1709
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- (iii) if $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive
SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1711
1712
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1713
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7 Extreme Applications in Cancer's Extreme Recognition

The cancer is the Extreme disease but the Extreme model is going to figure out what's going on this Extreme phenomenon. The special Extreme case of this Extreme disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Extreme recognition of the cancer could help to find some Extreme treatments for this Extreme disease. 1717
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In the following, some Extreme steps are Extreme devised on this disease. 1723

Step 1. (Extreme Definition) The Extreme recognition of the cancer in the long-term Extreme function. 1724
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Step 2. (Extreme Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Extreme model [it's called Extreme SuperHyperGraph] and the long Extreme cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Extreme SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. 1726
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Step 3. (Extreme Model) There are some specific Extreme models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Extreme models. The moves and the Extreme traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions or the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in those Extreme Extreme SuperHyperModels. 1733
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8 Case 1: The Initial Extreme Steps Toward Extreme SuperHyperBipartite as Extreme SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Extreme Solution) In the Extreme Figure (29), the Extreme SuperHyperBipartite is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. By using the Extreme Figure (29) and the Table (4), the Extreme SuperHyperBipartite is obtained. 1744
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The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (29), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1748
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Figure 29. a Extreme SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Extreme SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Figure 30. a Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

9 Case 2: The Increasing Extreme Steps Toward Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite as Extreme SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Extreme Solution) In the Extreme Figure (30), the Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. By using the Extreme Figure (30) and the Table (5), the Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (30), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed. The SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s

recognitions?

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Question 10.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions?*

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Question 10.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

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Question 10.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions?*

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Problem 10.5. *The SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer's recognitions and they're based on SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, are there else?*

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Problem 10.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

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Problem 10.7. *What's the independent research based on Cancer's recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

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11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

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In this section, concluding remarks and closing remarks are represented. The drawbacks of this research are illustrated. Some benefits and some advantages of this research are highlighted.

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This research uses some approaches to make Extreme SuperHyperGraphs more understandable. In this endeavor, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. For that sake in the second definition, the main definition of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new definition for the Extreme SuperHyperGraph, the new SuperHyperNotion, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, finds the convenient background to implement some results based on that. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Extreme SuperHyperClasses are the cases of this research on the modeling of the regions where are under the attacks of the cancer to recognize this disease as it's mentioned on the title "Cancer's Recognitions". To formalize the instances on the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, the new SuperHyperClasses and SuperHyperClasses, are introduced. Some general results are gathered in the section on the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. The clarifications, instances and literature reviews have taken the whole way through. In this research, the literature reviews have fulfilled the lines containing the notions and the results. The SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the "Cancer's Recognitions" and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix "SuperHyper" refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. In the Table (6), benefits and avenues for this research are, figured out, pointed out and spoken out.

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Table 6. An Overlook On This Research And Beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining Extreme SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. SuperHyperStable-Decompositions	
3. Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. Modeling of Cancer's Recognitions	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

12 Extreme SuperHyperDuality But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 12.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$ and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$ and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality.

Definition 12.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme

- rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
 conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1846
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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of 1851
 Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1852
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1853
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme 1854
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme 1855
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of 1856
 an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive 1857
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form 1858
 the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its 1859
 Extreme coefficient; 1860
- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of 1861
 Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1862
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a 1863
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme 1864
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme 1865
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of 1866
 a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive 1867
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form 1868
 the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its 1869
 Extreme coefficient; 1870
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1871
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1872
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1873
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality 1874
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme 1875
 SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme 1876
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 1877
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1878
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1879
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1880
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a 1881
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality 1882
 of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high 1883
 Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and 1884
 Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme 1885
 SuperHyperDuality; 1886
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either 1887
 of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1888
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1889
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme 1890
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme 1891
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices 1892
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality 1893
 conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme 1894

SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 1895
1896

- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of 1897
Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1898
v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a 1899
Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme 1900
SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme 1901
number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices 1902
of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality 1903
consequence Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme 1904
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the 1905
Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient. 1906

Example 12.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ 1907
in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items. 1908

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme 1909
SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1910
 E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme 1911
SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of 1912
Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, 1913
 E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no 1914
Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme 1915
SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1916

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme 1917
SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1918
 E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme 1919
SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's 1920
only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, 1921
 V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a 1922
Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every 1923
given Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1924

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme 1925
SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1926

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1927
1928

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1929
1930

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1931
1932

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{3i+24^3_{i=0}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1^7_{i=0}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1933
1934

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1935
1936

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1937
1938

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1939
1940

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1941
1942

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1943
1944

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1945
1946

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1947
1948

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1949
1950

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1951
1952

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (2 \times 1 \times 2) + (2 \times 4 \times 5)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1953
1954

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1955
1956

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (2 \times 2 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1957
1958

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1959
1960

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1961
1962

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1963
1964

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 9 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 9 + 12 \times 6z^2. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 1965
1966

Proposition 12.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then 1967
1968

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)} \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1969

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 1970
1971

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. 1972
1973
□ 1974

Example 12.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperDuality. 1975
1976
1977

Proposition 12.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$.
Then

1978
1979

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \frac{|\{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}|}{3}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z \frac{|\{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}|}{3}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \frac{|\{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}|}{3}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)} \frac{|\{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}|}{3z}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1980

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

1981
1982

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
straightforward. $\square$

1983
1984
1985

Example 12.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in
the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

1986
1987
1988

Proposition 12.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
Then

1989
1990

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} |z|. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1991

$$P : V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\ &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ &\quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is

straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \\
 \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \\
 \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 12.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
 & = \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 & = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) choose |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
 & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 & = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| choose 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 12.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$.

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i| E_i^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^* |_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}|z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2^*, \\ \dots, \\ E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}^*, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}+1}^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z^* \equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z^*. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperDuality proposes some longest SuperHyperDuality excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

13 Extreme SuperHyperJoin But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 13.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; 2072
2073
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; 2074
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2076
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin. 2077
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Definition 13.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperJoin). 2079

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 2080
2081

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; 2082
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- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; 2089
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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2096
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- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2106
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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme 2116
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SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;

- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 13.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperJoin. 2163
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2169
2170

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2171
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2173
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2175
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2177
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2179
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2181
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2183
2184

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2185
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2187
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2189
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2191
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2193
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2195
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2197
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2199
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2201
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0}^5}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses.

Proposition 13.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}} V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} |z|. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's
a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
straightforward. □

Example 13.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by
the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the
connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel
(25), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite

$ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward.

□ 2260

Example 13.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHG : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHG : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)_{z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL}^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

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minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL}^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme

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SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme

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SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$,

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in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$.

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Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin} = \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}.
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperJoin proposes some longest SuperHyperJoin excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

14 Extreme SuperHyperPerfect But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 14.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect.

Definition 14.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph

- $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2330-2334
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2335-2341
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2342-2351
- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2352-2361
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2362-2369
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2370-2377

- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either
of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme
v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
consequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the
Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme
v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a
Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
consequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the
Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 14.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$
in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme
SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of
Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no
Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme
SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme
SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's
only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex,
 V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a
Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every
given Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2416
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2418
2419

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2420
2421

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2422
2423

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{3i+24}_{i=0}^3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^7\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2424
2425

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2426
2427

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2428
2429

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{23}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, V_{15}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2430
2431

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2432
2433

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1, E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_6, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 2z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2434
2435

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2436
2437

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_3, E_9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2438
2439

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2440
2441

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2442
2443

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2444
2445

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2446
2447

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2448
2449

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2450
2451

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2452
2453

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2454
2455

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2456
2457

Proposition 14.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then 2458
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2460

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2461
2462

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. 2463
2464
□ 2465

Example 14.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperPerfect. 2466
2467
2468

Proposition 14.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then 2469
2470

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2471

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2472
2473

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. 2474
2475
2476 $\square$

Example 14.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect. 2477
2478
2479

Proposition 14.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then 2480
2481

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = |i | E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} |z. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ = (PERFECT\ MATCHING). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ = (OTHERWISE). \end{aligned}$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ = (PERFECT\ MATCHING). \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)$$

$$z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}|$$

$$= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\},$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ = (OTHERWISE)0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 14.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

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minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} |z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel

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$ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperPerfect proposes some longest SuperHyperPerfect excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

15 Extreme SuperHyperTotal But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 15.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal.

Definition 15.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

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- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme

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number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the
Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 15.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$
in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme
SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of
Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no
Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme
SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme
SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's
only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex,
 V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a
Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every
given Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2665
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2667
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2669
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2671
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2673
2674

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2675
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2677
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2679
2680

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2681
2682

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2683
2684

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2685
2686

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2687
2688

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2689
2690

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2691
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2693
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2695
2696

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_6, E_{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (|V| - 1)z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2697
2698

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2699
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2701
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Proposition 15.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 2703
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} \\
& = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2705

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\
\dots
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2706
2707

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. 2708
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Example 15.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperTotal. 2711
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Proposition 15.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then 2714
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} - 1) \\
& z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} \\
& = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & \frac{E^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}-1}}}{V^{EXTERNAL}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}-1}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i(i-1)| E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} |z^2|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1) \\
 &z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
&= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\
& \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= z \min_{|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
&= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
&= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 15.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESH B : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESH B : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
&= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\
& \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
&= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
&= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 2772

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2773
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 2774

Example 15.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2775
 $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme 2776
 SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme 2777
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, 2778
 in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal. 2779

Proposition 15.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. 2780
 Then, 2781

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2782

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel 2783
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2784

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 2785
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is 2786
 straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi 2787
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. The 2788
 unique embedded SuperHyperTotal proposes some longest SuperHyperTotal excerpt 2789
 from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 2790

Example 15.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme 2791
 SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained 2792
 Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme 2793
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in 2794
 the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal. 2795

16 Extreme SuperHyperConnected But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 16.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected.

Definition 16.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of

an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

(vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 16.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items. 2891
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- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperConnected. 2893
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperConnected. 2902
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2910
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2913
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2916
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2919
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2922
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2925
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2928
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=11}^9, V_{22}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 2931
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2949
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2952
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2955
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2958
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2961
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2964
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2967
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2970
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Proposition 16.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 2972
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2974

$$\begin{aligned}P : \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}.\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2975
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$$\begin{aligned}V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHPP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHCC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ & \quad z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} \\ & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality} - 1}, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality} - 1}^{EXTERNAL}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHCC : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ SuperHyperConnected} = \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality} z. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ R-SuperHyperConnected} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ R-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} = z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \underset{z}{\min} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z_{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperConnected} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}|z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V^{EXTERNAL}_i, E^*_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperConnected proposes some longest SuperHyperConnected excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

17 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them date back on March 09, 2023.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 1 and issue 1 with pages 06-14. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [87]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

In some articles are titled “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs ” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [101]** by Henry Garrett

(2023), “The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [102]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [103]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [104]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [107]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique” in **Ref. [108]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [111]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [114]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [115]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [116]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [117]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [118]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [119]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [130]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)” in **Ref. [131]** by Henry Garrett (2022), and [4–55, 57–131], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph.

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [132]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 3230 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs” and published by Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United State. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [133]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 4117 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Neutrosophic Duality” and published by Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s

done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd. 3210

See the seminal scientific researches [1,2]. The formalization of the notions on the 3211
 framework of notions In SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions In 3212
 SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory 3213
 at [4–55,57–131]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high 3214
 readers, 3230 and 4117 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [132,133]. 3215

– 3216

References 3217

1. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Co-degree and Neutrosophic Degree alongside Chromatic Numbers in the Setting of Some Classes Related to Neutrosophic Hypergraphs*”, J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res 1(1) (2022) 06-14. 3218
3219
3220
2. Henry Garrett, “*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09) 3221
3222
3223
3224
3. Henry Garrett, “*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (<https://www.opastpublishers.com/open-access-articles/some-super-hyper-degrees-and-cosuper-hyper-degrees-on-neutrosophic-super-hyper-graphs-and-super-hyper-graphs-alongside-a.pdf>) 3225
3226
3227
3228
3229
3230
4. Garrett, Henry. “*0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>. 3231
<https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942> 3232
3233
3234
3235
3236
5. Garrett, Henry. “*0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>. 3237
<https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724> 3238
3239
3240
3241
6. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 3242
3243
3244
3245
7. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 3246
3247
3248
3249
8. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 3250
3251
3252
9. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New* 3253
3254

- Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*", Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 3255-3258
10. Henry Garrett, "*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer's Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*", Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 3259-3262
11. Henry Garrett, "*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*", Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 3263-3266
12. Henry Garrett, "*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer's Circumstances Where Cancer's Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*", Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 3267-3270
13. Henry Garrett, "*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer's Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*", Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3271-3273
14. Henry Garrett, "*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*", Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 3274-3277
15. Henry Garrett, "*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*", Preprints 2023, 2023010044 3278-3280
16. Henry Garrett, "*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer's Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*", Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 3281-3283
17. Henry Garrett, "*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer's Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*", Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3284-3287
18. Henry Garrett, "*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*", Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 3288-3291
19. Henry Garrett, "*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer's Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*", Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 3292-3294
20. Henry Garrett, "*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer's Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*", Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 3295-3299

21. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 3300
3301
3302
22. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 3303
3304
3305
3306
23. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 3307
3308
3309
3310
24. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23525.68320). 3311
3312
3313
25. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20170.24000). 3314
3315
3316
26. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Neighbors As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36475.59683). 3317
3318
3319
27. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Clique-Neighbors In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29764.71046). 3320
3321
3322
28. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18780.87683). 3323
3324
3325
29. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique- Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27169.48487). 3326
3327
3328
30. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Cut As Hyper Click On Super Cliche*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26134.01603). 3329
3330
3331
31. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Cliff By Hyper Cling Of Clique-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27392.30721). 3332
3333
3334
32. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Spin On Super Spacy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33028.40321). 3335
3336
3337
33. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By List- Coloring As Hyper List On Super Lisle*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21389.20966). 3338
3339
3340
34. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Lith By Hyper Lite Of List-Coloring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16356.04489). 3341
3342
3343

35. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 3344
3345
3346
36. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 3347
3348
3349
37. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 3350
3351
3352
38. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 3353
3354
3355
39. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 3356
3357
3358
40. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 3359
3360
3361
41. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 3362
3363
3364
42. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163). 3365
3366
3367
43. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401). 3368
3369
3370
44. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720). 3371
3372
3373
45. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165). 3374
3375
3376
46. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003). 3377
3378
3379
47. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962). 3380
3381
3382
48. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280). 3383
3384
3385
49. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086). 3386
3387
3388

50. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404). 3389
3390
3391
51. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968). 3392
3393
3394
52. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003). 3395
3396
3397
53. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641). 3398
3399
3400
54. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967). 3401
3402
3403
55. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121). 3404
3405
3406
56. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 3407
3408
3409
57. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 3410
3411
3412
58. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446). 3413
3414
3415
59. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961). 3416
3417
3418
60. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361). 3419
3420
3421
61. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125). 3422
3423
3424
62. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321). 3425
3426
3427
63. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441). 3428
3429
3430
64. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367). 3431
3432
3433

65. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048). 3434
3435
3436
66. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286). 3437
3438
3439
67. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602). 3440
3441
3442
68. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285). 3443
3444
3445
69. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569). 3446
3447
3448
70. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206). 3449
3450
3451
71. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320). 3452
3453
3454
72. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 3455
3456
3457
73. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 3458
3459
3460
74. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 3461
3462
3463
75. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 3464
3465
3466
76. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 3467
3468
3469
77. Henry Garrett, “New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 3470
3471
3472
3473
78. Henry Garrett, “New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 3474
3475
3476
3477

79. Henry Garrett, “New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960).
3478
3479
3480
3481
80. Henry Garrett, “A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040).
3482
3483
3484
3485
81. Henry Garrett, “A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125).
3486
3487
3488
3489
82. Henry Garrett, “A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089).
3490
3491
3492
3493
83. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562).
3494
3495
3496
3497
84. Henry Garrett, “Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968).
3498
3499
3500
85. Henry Garrett, “Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525).
3501
3502
3503
86. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485).
3504
3505
3506
87. Henry Garrett, “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 2(1) (2023) 35-47.
3507
3508
3509
3510
88. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1).
3511
3512
3513
3514
89. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1).
3515
3516
3517
3518
90. Henry Garrett, “The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204).
3519
3520
3521
3522
3523

91. Henry Garrett,“(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 3524
3525
3526
3527
3528
92. Henry Garrett,“Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 3529
3530
3531
3532
93. Henry Garrett,“SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 3533
3534
3535
94. Henry Garrett,“Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 3536
3537
3538
3539
95. Henry Garrett,“Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 3540
3541
3542
3543
96. Henry Garrett,“Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 3544
3545
3546
97. Henry Garrett, “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 3547
3548
3549
3550
3551
3552
98. Henry Garrett,“Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 3553
3554
3555
3556
99. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 3557
3558
3559
3560
100. Henry Garrett, “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 3561
3562
3563
3564
101. Henry Garrett,“*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 3565
3566
3567

102. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 3568
3569
3570
3571
103. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 3572
3573
3574
3575
104. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 3576
3577
3578
3579
105. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 3580
3581
3582
3583
106. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3584
3585
3586
107. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 3587
3588
3589
108. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 3590
3591
3592
3593
109. Henry Garrett, “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3594
3595
3596
3597
110. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 3598
3599
3600
3601
111. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 3602
3603
3604
3605
112. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 3606
3607
3608
113. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 3609
3610
3611

114. Henry Garrett, “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 3612
3613
3614
115. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 3615
3616
3617
116. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 3618
3619
3620
117. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 3621
3622
3623
3624
118. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 3625
3626
3627
119. Henry Garrett, “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 3628
3629
3630
3631
120. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 3632
3633
3634
121. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 3635
3636
3637
122. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 3638
3639
3640
3641
3642
123. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 3643
3644
3645
3646
3647
124. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 3648
3649
3650
125. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 3651
3652
3653
126. Henry Garrett, “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 3654
3655
3656
3657

127. Henry Garrett, “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 3658
3659
3660
3661
128. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 3662
3663
3664
3665
129. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966). 3666
3667
3668
3669
130. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244). 3670
3671
3672
131. Henry Garrett, “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160). 3673
3674
3675
3676
132. Henry Garrett, (2022). “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”, Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United States. ISBN: 979-1-59973-725-6 (http://fs.unm.edu/BeyondNeutrosophicGraphs.pdf). 3677
3678
3679
3680
133. Henry Garrett, (2022). “*Neutrosophic Duality*”, Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. ISBN: 978-1-59973-743-0 (http://fs.unm.edu/NeutrosophicDuality.pdf). 3681
3682
3683
3684